

PyMOL Cheatsheet - Biodesign Edition

Core Navigation

- Rotate: Left-click and drag
- Zoom: Scroll wheel or right-click and drag up/down
- Pan: Middle-click (or Shift+left-click) and drag

Basic Commands

- load filename.pdb
- show cartoon, all
- color green, chain A
- hide everything
- label resi 45, name

Selections

- select my_residue, resi 45
- select helix, ss h
- select chainA, chain A
- select oxygen, elem O

Styles

- show sticks, selection
- show surface, selection
- set cartoon_transparency, 0.5
- bg_color white

Export

- ray
- png image.png
- mplay (to play movie)

AlphaFold Tips

- color b-factor

- spectrum b, blue_white_red, minimum=50, maximum=100